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Design, CPM-Based Scheduling, and Economic Evaluation of a Rooftop Solar Energy System in the Bursa Free Zone

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ABSTRACT

This study addresses the rising energy costs and carbon emission challenges by designing a solar energy system to meet energy demands in the Bursa Free Zone, aligning with sustainability and governmental energy efficiency standards. Rooftops of industrial facilities were evaluated as installation sites for photovoltaic (PV) systems. Using tools such as PV-SOL, PVsyst, and SketchUp, feasibility reports were prepared, and a 1,558-kWh capacity solar system was proposed. This system is expected to generate approximately 2,111,405 kWh of electricity annually. In addition to the technical design, a detailed project scheduling and optimization process was conducted using the Critical Path Method (CPM). The goal was to identify critical project activities and evaluate the potential for duration reduction. Project crashing scenarios were analysed using QM for Windows V5 and LINGO optimization software. Among several scenarios, the most efficient was shortening the project duration by one month at an additional cost of \$8,725, offering the best time-cost trade-off. The engineering economic analysis was conducted in parallel, evaluating the project's financial performance over a 25-year lifecycle. Key metrics such as payback period and net present value (NPV) were calculated. The study also examined the financial benefits of project acceleration. This integrated approach—combining solar energy system design, CPM-based project scheduling, optimization software, and engineering economics—provides a comprehensive framework for sustainable energy implementation and efficient project management.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the rapid increase in population and industrialization, global energy demand continues to rise. As energy is a limited resource in nature, its production and consumption have created a serious imbalance [1]. In this context, energy security, efficiency, and environmental sustainability have become top priorities for many countries. Renewable energy sources are among the key alternatives, as they are self-replenishing and have low depletion risks. These systems offer several advantages, including fast returns after installation, low operational costs, and minimal environmental impact.

Moreover, the use of renewables reduces foreign energy dependence and lowers national energy expenditures.

In the first phase of this study, general information about renewable energy systems is presented. Subsequently, a rooftop solar power plant model was designed for Facility 1 in the free zone, along with a critical path analysis and time-cost trade-off evaluation. During implementation, various simulation tools such as Global Solar Atlas, Helioscope, PV-SOL, and PVSyst were employed.[2]

In the final phase, the project was analysed using the Critical Path Method (CPM), and time-cost trade-off analyses were conducted to determine the optimal project duration. These project management efforts were coordinated with engineering economic analyses, including evaluations of the project's payback period, net return over a 25-year period, and the financial impact of completing the project one month earlier.

1.1 Solar Energy

A significant portion of solar radiation is either absorbed or reflected before reaching the Earth's surface. Approximately 17.5% heats the atmosphere, 35% is reflected back into space by clouds and the surface, while the remaining 47.5% reaches the Earth and is converted into thermal energy. While solar irradiance outside the atmosphere is about 1370 W/m², it ranges between 0 and 1100 W/m² at ground level due to atmospheric interference. Even this small fraction of incident solar energy far exceeds the total global energy demand [3].

The sun is one of the most fundamental energy sources on Earth, serving as the origin of all energy flows. Through various transformation processes, solar energy can be converted into other forms such as wind, ocean waves, temperature gradients in the seas, and biomass [4]. It is used both for heating and electricity generation, making it a clean and environmentally friendly energy alternative [5]. Due to its inexhaustibility, ease of operation, lack of mechanical wear, modular structure, quick installation (often within one year), and long service life, the global use of solar energy is rapidly increasing [6].

Turkey, thanks to its geopolitical location, has significant potential for solar electricity generation [7]. In regions with high solar irradiance, such as Turkey, solar energy stands out as a promising alternative energy source. Figure 1 presents the Karapınar Solar Power Plant in Turkey, while Figure 2 illustrates the country's solar radiation levels. Although Turkey records an average of 2640 hours of sunlight per year, commercial-scale use of solar energy remains limited due to high installation costs [8].

Figure 1. Karapınar Solar Power Plant

Figure 2. Solar Energy Potential Map [9]

Table 1 presents the installed capacities of operational solar power plants worldwide, with China, the United States, and Japan ranking as the top three countries. Furthermore, According to the Figure 3, by the end of 2028, the global installed solar power capacity is projected to reach between 4.5 and 6 terawatts.

Table 1. Installed Solar Power Capacities by Country (Energy Atlas, 2022) [10]

S/N	Country	Update	Installed Capacity (MW)
1	China	Dec 2022	393.032
2	USA	Dec 2022	113.015
3	Japan	Dec 2022	78.833
4	Germany	Dec 2022	66.554
5	India	Dec 2022	63.146
6	Australia	Dec 2022	26.792
7	Italy	Dec 2022	25.083
8	Brazil	Dec 2022	24.079
9	Netherlands	Dec 2022	22.590
10	South Korea	Dec 2022	20.975
11	Spain	Dec 2022	20.518
12	Vietnam	Dec 2022	18.474
13	France	Dec 2022	17.419
14	United Kingdom	Dec 2022	14.412
15	Türkiye	Apr 2024	12.661
16	Poland	Dec 2022	11.167
17	Taiwan	Dec 2022	9.724
18	Mexico	Dec 2022	9.026
19	Ukraine	Dec 2022	8.062
20	South Africa	Dec 2022	5.990

Global Solar Power Installed Capacity Expected to Exceed 2 Terawatts by Year-End

The global installed solar power capacity is expected to exceed 2 terawatts by the end of this year, reaching 2,2 terawatts with the addition of an estimated 544 gigawatts.

Figure 3. Global Installed Solar Power Capacity [11]

2 SOLAR POWER PLANT PROJECT IN BURSA FREE ZONE

The Free Zone model in Turkey was established under Law No. 3218 to promote export-oriented investment and production, accelerate foreign direct investment and technology transfer, and enhance international trade activities [5]. In this study, the energy demands of facilities within the Bursa Free Zone were analysed, and the design of an alternative energy system was developed accordingly. PV-SOL and PVsyst solar simulation software were employed in the system's design. Data obtained from these tools enabled both technical and economic evaluations of the project.

During the plant design, photovoltaic (PV) panel capacity was planned based on the agreed grid connection capacity, with a margin allowing slight oversizing beyond contractual limits [12]. The PV system's energy output, power losses, monthly performance ratios, and financial indicators were primarily assessed using the PVsyst simulation tool [3]. Figure 4 shows the solar irradiance and sunshine duration data specific to the Gemlik district of Bursa, which were essential in evaluating site suitability. Figure 5 presents a bird's-eye view of the selected facility's location and rooftop, obtained via Google Earth, to support visual site assessment and installation planning.

Figure 4. Gemlik District Radiation Values and Figure 5. The facility in the Free Zone Sunshine Durations [9]

2.1 Simulation Process and PVsyst Results

In this section, the structures of the planned solar power plants on available rooftop areas were modelled and analysed using PV-SOL and PVsyst software. The modelling included detailed 3D simulations along with shadow analysis. The meteorological database used was Meteonorm, specifically the Meteonorm 8.1 dataset for Bursa from 2005–2013.

Table 2 presents the energy consumption data of Facility 1 across three different time periods. Figure 6 shows the system's preliminary visual outputs, generated first with technical drawings in AutoCAD and then modeled in 3D using SketchUp prior to installation

Figure 6. Solar energy system modeling visuals for Facility 1

Table 2. The monthly energy needs for Facility 1

Period	T1 (kWh)	T2 (kWh)	T3 (kWh)	Total (kWh)
2024				
January	21.186,185	9.695,613	13.865,009	44.746,81
February	20.538,061	9.437,171	13.412,735	43.388,97
March	21.050,907	9.348,331	12.962,481	43361,72
April	18.113,149	8.262,067	12.316,376	38.691,59
May	21.582,14	9.620,137	13.874,526	45.076,80
June	20.124,54	9.408,15	13.322,52	42.855,21
July	24.007,86	10.824,03	15.854,13	50.686,02
August	25.523,1	11.256,66	16.365,42	53.145,18
September	23.128,11	10.534,23	15.396,66	49.059,00
October	19.946,52	9.540,63	13.757,22	43.244,37
November	21.130,56	9.281,88	13.535,73	43.948,17
December	16.930,53	7.089,75	10.737,09	34.757,37
TOTAL	253.262	114.299	165.400	532.960

Table 3 presents the datasheet specifications of the solar panels planned for use in the solar power plant design, while Table 4 provides technical details of the inverter systems that convert the DC power from PV modules into AC power.[13]

For the solar energy system designed for Facility 1, the PVsyst simulation program was used to model and evaluate key parameters such as panel and inverter specifications, system losses, and estimated energy output[14]. The simulation results and visual outputs are shown in Figure 7.

Using the PVsyst software, the rooftop solar power plant layout was modeled, and output reports were generated. Table 3 presents the number of PV modules, rooftop installation areas, module output power, number of inverters, and the total expected energy production [15].

Table 4 includes calculations for the energy demand of Facility 1 during period T1, the total energy to be generated by the plant, the estimated carbon emission reduction, and the equivalent number of trees saved.

Table 3. Solar Panel Specifications

Electrical Characteristics	Properties
Maximum power (Pmax)	590W
Open Circuit Voltage (Voc)	53.92V
Short circuit current (Isc)	13.96A
Optimum Operating Voltage (Vmp)	45.28V
Optimum Operating Current (Imp)	13.04A
Module Efficiency	21.1%
Power Tolerance	0 ~ +5W
Maximum System Voltage	1500V DC(UL/IEC)
Maximum Series Fuse Rating	25A
Operating Temperature	-40 C ~ +85 C
Number of Cells	156 (6 × 26)
Dimensions	2470mm×1133mm×35mm
Weight	29.4kg
Cell Type	Monocrystalline 182 × 91 mm
Product Warranty	12 Years
Power Output Warranty	30 Years

Table 4. Inverter Specifications

Electrical Characteristics	Properties
Maximum Input Voltage	1,100 V
Max. Current per MPPT	26 A
Max. Short Circuit Current per MPPT	40 A
Starting Voltage	200 V
MPPT Operating Voltage Range	200 V ~ 1,000 V
Nominal Input Voltage	720V@480 Vac, 600V@400 Vac, 570 V@380 Vac
Number of MPPT Trackers	10
Nominal AC Active Power	100,000 W
Maximum AC Apparent Power	110,000 VA
Nominal Output Voltage	480 V/ 400 V/ 380 V, 3W+(N)+PE
Nominal AC Grid Frequency	50 Hz / 60 Hz
Nominal Output Current	120.3 A @480 V, 144.4 A @400 V, 152.0 A @380 V
Maximum Output Current	133.7 A @480 V, 160.4 A @400 V, 168.8 A @380 V
Maximum Harmonic Distortion	<3%
Dimensions	1,035 x 700 x 365 mm
Weight	90 kg
Operating Temperature Range	-25°C ~ 60°C
Cooling Method	Smart Air Cooling
Protection Degree	IP66
Night Power Consumption	<3.5 W

Figure 7. PVsyst Outputs for Facility 1

Table 3. The results of the PVsyst study.

Facility Name	Roof Area (M ²)	PV Module Quantity (Units)	PV Output (kWp)	Inverter Quantity	Annual Production (kWh)
Facility 1	8,500	2,640	1,558	13	2,114,405

Table 4. Generated, consumed, and remaining electricity for the distribution system.

Facility Name	T1 Time Consumption (kWh)/Year	PV Module Production (kWh)/Year	Energy Remaining for System (kWh)/Year	Prevented CO2 Emission (Kg/Year)	Saved Tree Quantity (Units)
Facility 1	253,262	2,114,405	1,861,143	1,323,829	3,203

3 PROJECT MANAGEMENT, CPM ANALYSIS, AND TIME-COST TRADE-OFF

In this study, the project was analysed using the Critical Path Method (CPM). Based on the project and time-cost trade-off data provided in **Table 5**, the project scheduling and optimization were performed. The corresponding Activity-on-Arrow (AOA) network diagram is presented in **Figure 8**.

Table 5. CPM and Time-Cost Trade-Off Analysis Table

Activity	Description	Predecessors	Normal Time (day)	Crashed Time (d)	Normal Cost (\$)	Crash Cost (\$)
A	Feasibility studies	-	14	4	18,696	21,189
B	Technical design	A	14	4	12,464	14,334
C	Specifications and Tender process	B	14	4	31,160	35,522
D	Application process to distribution company	C	30	30	6,232	6,232
E	Notification process for invitation letter	D	3	3	6,232	6,232
F	Technical evaluation and approval process	E	90	90	6,232	6,232
G	Initiation of project orders	C	14	10	49,856	50,856
H	Shipment of design products	G	30	25	62,320	63,320
I	Structural Assembly	F	20	15	124,640	140,220
J	Installation of panels, inverters, and cabling	H,I	20	15	174,496	196,308
K	Connection and testing of transfer panels	J	7	7	124,640	124,640
L	Provisional acceptance and system commissioning	K	20	20	6,232	6,232

Figure 8. AOA Project Network of the Solar Power Plant Project

As shown in Table 6, the project is scheduled to be completed in 232 days under normal conditions. This solution was obtained using the CPM technique in the QM for Windows software. The same tool was also used to explore project crashing options. According to Table 7, the project duration can be reduced by 40 days—down to 192 days—with an additional cost of \$46,117.

Table 6 CPM solution

GES-PROJECT Solution						
Activity	Activity time	Early Start	Early Finish	Late Start	Late Finish	Slack
Project	232					
A	14	0	14	0	14	0
B	14	14	28	14	28	0
C	14	28	42	28	42	0
D	30	42	72	42	72	0
E	3	72	75	72	75	0
F	90	75	165	75	165	0
G	14	42	56	141	155	99
H	30	56	86	155	185	99
I	20	165	185	165	185	0
J	20	185	205	185	205	0
K	7	205	212	205	212	0
L	20	212	232	212	232	0

Table 7. Project Crashing table

Activity	Normal time	Crash time	Normal Cost	Crash Cost	Crash cost/pd	Crash by	Crashing cost
Project	232	192					
A	14	4	\$18696	\$21189	\$249,3	10	\$2493
B	14	4	\$12464	\$14334	\$187	10	\$1870
C	14	4	\$31160	\$35522	\$436,2	10	\$4362
D	30	30	\$6232	\$6232	\$0	0	\$0
E	3	3	\$6232	\$6232	\$0	0	\$0
F	90	90	\$6232	\$6232	\$0	0	\$0
G	14	10	\$49856	\$50856	\$250	0	\$0
H	30	25	\$62320	\$63320	\$200	0	\$0
I	20	15	\$1246...	\$1402...	\$3116	5	\$15580
J	20	15	\$1744...	\$1963...	\$4362,4	5	\$21812
K	7	7	\$1246...	\$1246...	\$0	0	\$0
L	20	20	\$6232	\$6232	\$0	0	\$0
TOTALS			\$6232...				\$46117

3.1 Time-Cost Trade-Off Using LINGO

The project was further analysed using the LINGO optimization software, and the corresponding linear programming (LP) model was developed. Various project crashing scenarios were evaluated using LINGO. Table 8 presents the notations, constraints, and descriptions used in the model, which was formulated based on the AOA project network shown in Figure 8.

Table 8. Notations, Constraints, and Descriptions Used in the LINGO Code

Notation / Constraint	Description
X1E	Earliest time at Node 1
Y12	Number of days Activity A (from Node 1 to 2) is crashed; max 10 days
X1L	Latest time at Node 1
$X2E - X1E + Y12 \geq 14$	Activity A requires a minimum of (14 - Y12) days between Nodes 1 and 2
$249.3 \times Y12$	Crashing Activity A by 1-day costs \$249.3
$X2L - X1L + Y12 \geq 14$	Latest time difference between Nodes 2 and 1 also must satisfy (14 - Y12)
BUDGET = 40000	Maximum available budget for crashing
$1872 \times X12E$	Finishing 1 day earlier saves \$1,872 (based on \$56,170.4 gain over 30 days)
CRASH ≤ BUDGET	Total crashing cost must not exceed the available budget
X12L = X12E	Early and late finish times at final Node 12 must be equal
@GIN(X12E)	X12E is an integer
$X12L \leq 202$	Project should be completed in ≤202 days
END	Indicates the end of the LINGO LP model

LINGO:

```

MIN=(X1E+X2E+X3E+X4E+X5E+X6E+X7E+X8E+X9E+X10E+X11E+1872*X12E)
(X1L+X2L+X3L+X4L+X5L+X6L+X7L+X8L+X9L+X10L+X11L+X12L) + CRASH;

CRASH = 249,3*Y12+ 187*Y23+ 436,2*Y34+ 250*Y48+ 200*Y89+ 3116*Y79+ 4362,4*Y910;
X2E-X1E + Y12 >= 14;           X2L-X1L + Y12 >= 14;           BUDGET =40000;
X3E-X2E + Y23 >= 14;           X3L-X2L + Y23 >= 14;           CRASH<= BUDGET;
X4E-X3E + Y34 >= 14;           X4L-X3L + Y34 >= 14;           Y12<= 10;
X5E-X4E >= 30;                 X5L-X4L >= 30;                 Y23<= 10;
X6E-X5E >= 3;                 X6L-X5L >= 3;                 Y34<= 10;
X7E-X6E >= 90;                 X7L-X6L >= 90;                 Y48<= 4;
X8E-X4E + Y48 >= 14;           X8L-X4L + Y48 >= 14;           Y89<= 5;
X9E-X8E + Y89 >= 30;           X9L-X8L + Y89 >= 30;           Y79<= 5;
X9E-X7E >= 20;                 X9L-X7L >= 20;                 Y910<= 5;
X10E-X9E + Y910>= 20;         X10L-X9L + Y910>= 20;         X12L = X12E;
X11E-X10E >= 7;                X11L-X10L >= 7;                X12L <= 202;
X12E-X11E >= 20;               X12L-X11L >= 20;               @GIN(X12E);
END
    
```

Initially, the project was solved under normal conditions, resulting in a duration of 232 days. It was then fully crashed to determine the minimum possible duration, which was found to be 192 days. When all activities were shortened to their maximum allowable durations (i.e., all Y_{ij} values at maximum), the total cost was calculated as \$48,117. In contrast, the QM for Windows solution produced a lower cost of \$46,117 because it excluded the crashing of activities Y48 and Y89, which had no impact on project duration. Thus, the additional \$2,000 was identified as an unnecessary cost. Using LINGO, when only the essential activities were crashed, the total cost again matched the optimized value of \$46,117.

In another scenario, assuming that each day the project finishes earlier yields a gain of \$1,872 (based on $1872 \times X12E$), the project was shortened by 30 days for a cost of \$8,725. Beyond this point, the software did not allow further reduction, as it would not be cost-effective.

When a budget constraint of \$40,000 was introduced along with the requirement for integer time durations, LINGO optimized the project to 194 days using \$37,392.2. The remaining \$2,600 was insufficient to reduce the project by even one additional day.

In conclusion, the most cost-effective scenario was to shorten the project by 30 days at a cost of \$8,725. Further crashing beyond this point would result in diminishing returns, with the absolute maximum reduction capped at 40 days.

4 CONCLUSION

Within the scope of this study, a rooftop solar power system using 2,604 PV modules with a total installed capacity of 1,558 kWp was designed. This system is expected to generate approximately 2,114,405 kWh annually, preventing 1,324 tons of CO₂ emissions and saving 3,204 trees. The total installation cost was calculated as 623,200 USD.

Assuming that all generated electricity will be consumed locally and the March 2024 electricity selling price is 0.11961 USD/kWh, the system is projected to yield an annual income of 252,904 USD. Accordingly, the investment payback period is estimated at around 2.5 years.

Table 9 shows that the PV system will face annual efficiency degradation—2.5% in the first year and 0.6% in subsequent years. It also assumes that the electricity selling price will increase annually by $f=2.9\%$, based on the average U.S. inflation over 20 years.

Table 9. Present Value Calculation of Project Cash Flow Over Time

Year (k)	Designed Annual Electricity Production (kWh)	Annual PV Module Efficiency Loss (%)	Electricity Production in Year k (kWh)	Electricity Sale Price (USD)	Cash Flow (USD)	Present Value (P_0) of Cash Flow $f=2.9\%$	Cumulative Present Value (P_0) ($f=2.9\%$)	Present Value if Completed 1 Month Early (monthly MARR= $i=1\%$)
1	2,114,405.0	0.0	2,114,405.0	0.120	252,904.0	245,776.5	-377,423.5	248,234.2
2	2,114,405.0	2.5	2,061,544.9	0.123	253,732.2	239,632.1	-137,791.5	242,028.4
3	2,061,545.0	0.6	2,049,175.7	0.127	259,524.0	238,194.3	100,402.8	240,576.2
...
25	1,805,894.0	0.6	1,795,058.6	0.238	426,398.0	208,655.9	4,993,836.0	210,742.5
TOTAL						5,617,036.0		5,673,206.4
DIFFERENCE = 5,673,206.4 - 5,617,036.0						56,170.4		

The table includes annual cash flows, which are discounted to present values (P_0) using a 2.9% rate. Although the first year's income is not sufficient for payback, the project breaks even in year three and achieves a net present value (NPV) of 4,993,836 USD over 25 years.

If completed one month earlier, using a monthly MARR (Minimum attractive rate of return) of 1%, the project's NPV increases by 56,170 USD, or approximately 1,872 USD per day. Based on risk-free rates, country risk, and sector-specific risks, the recommended USD-based MARR for Turkey ranges between 14% and 22% annually; this study conservatively uses an annual MARR of 12.68%.

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